

SHAC++: A Neural Network to Rule All Differentiable Simulators

Appendix Material

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A Environments

Table 1: Comparison of Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning Environments/Frameworks

Feature	VMAS	PettingZoo	SMAC	MA-MuJoCo	PyBullet	Neural MMO	Melting Pot
Key Focus	Fast, Vectorized 2D Physics (PyTorch)	Standardized MARL API (Collection)	StarCraft II Micromanagement	Multi-Agent Robotics (MuJoCo tasks)	General 3D Physics Engine	Large-Scale Agent Survival/Econ.	Social Dilemmas / Cooperation
Single/Multi (can do Single)	Primarily Multi	Primarily Multi (API standard)	Multi Only	Primarily Multi (adaptations)	Both	Multi Only (Massively)	Multi Only
Differentiable	Yes	No	No	No	No (standard use)	No	No
Generality	Medium (Physics-based, PyTorch)	Very High (via wrapped envs)	Low (Specific game benchmark)	Medium (MuJoCo robotics)	High (General physics)	Medium (Large-scale agent focus)	Medium (Social dilemmas focus)

Figure 1: VMAS environments used in the experiments.

In this section, we provide a detailed overview of the environments used to evaluate the SHAC++ algorithm. For our experiments, we selected four vectorized scenarios from VMAS (Vectorized Multi-Agent Simulator), which offers an ideal balance of features for our research objectives.

VMAS stands out among alternative multi-agent reinforcement learning frameworks such as PettingZoo [6], SMAC [4], MA-MuJoCo [2], PyBullet [1], Neural MMO [5], and Melting Pot [3]. As summarized in Table 1, VMAS provides several key advantages for our work:

- **Multi-Agent Framework:** VMAS is specifically designed for multi-agent scenarios, making it appropriate for our experimental setup.
- **Differentiable Physics:** Unlike most alternatives, VMAS offers a differentiable physics engine that enables gradient-based optimization techniques.
- **Vectorized Implementation:** The framework supports parallel execution of multiple environments, significantly improving training efficiency.
- **Physics-based Simulation:** VMAS provides realistic modeling of agent interactions and dynamics through its physics engine.
- **Open Source Accessibility:** The codebase is fully accessible, allowing necessary modifications for our experiments.

While VMAS provides differentiable transition functions across all tasks, its reward functions are generally non-differentiable. To address this limitation, we implemented custom differentiable reward functions where possible to replicate the original VMAS behavior. Consequently, some scenarios are compatible with all tested algorithms (PPO, SHAC, and SHAC++), while others can only be used with PPO and SHAC++.

An additional consideration is that VMAS often provides agents with partial observations rather than complete state information. In some scenarios, these observations contain sufficient information to predict subsequent states, while in others they do not. This partial observability presents a particular challenge for SHAC++, as its world model must operate with incomplete information. In contrast, SHAC computes gradients with access to the full world state. We deliberately maintained these observability constraints to assess SHAC++’s performance under more realistic conditions.

Figure 1 illustrates the four VMAS environments used in our experiments, which are detailed in the following subsections.

A.1 Dispersion

In the Dispersion task, n agents must reach n randomly placed goals. In Fig. 1a, the agents are represented by blue dots, while the goals are depicted as green dots.

Each agent has a continuous 2-dimensional action space, bounded between -1 and 1 , to represent acceleration along the x - and y -axes, respectively. Each agent observes its own position, velocity, and relative position to each goal. As a consequence, the world model has sufficient information to accurately predict the next states.

Each agent receives a reward of 1 upon reaching a goal, making the maximum possible reward n . While the transition function is differentiable, the reward function is not. Consequently, only PPO and SHAC++ are applicable to this scenario.

A.2 Transport

In the Transport problem, n agents work together to push a package to a randomly placed target location. In Fig. 1b, the agents are represented by blue dots, the package is shown as a red square, and the goal is depicted as a green circle. The more agents collaborate to push the package, the faster they can reach the goal and achieve the maximum reward.

Each agent has a continuous 2-dimensional action space, bounded between -1 and 1 , to represent acceleration along the x - and y -axes, respectively. Each agent observes its own position, velocity, the relative position to the package, and the relative position between the package and the goal. As a consequence, the world model has sufficient information to accurately predict the next states.

Each agent receives a reward proportional to the distance between the initial position of the package and the goal. Consequently, the maximum reward corresponds to the distance between the package and the goal. Since the maximum reward varies across environments, we only plot a reference line representing good performance. Although this reward function is differentiable, the implementation provided by VMAS is not. Therefore, we created a custom reward function to replicate the original one used by all algorithms (SHAC++, SHAC, and PPO).

A.3 Discovery

In the Discovery task, n agents aim to collect as many randomly placed goals as possible. When they successfully collect k goals, another k goals are randomly placed. To collect a goal, at least s agents must be in proximity to it. In Fig. 1c, the agents are represented by blue dots, while the goals are depicted as green dots. The proximity area is indicated by a dashed circle. In our experiments, we set $s = 2$ and $k = 7$ when $n > 1$. When $n = 1$, we set $s = 1$ and $k = 7$.

Each agent has a continuous 2-dimensional action space, bounded between -1 and 1 , to represent acceleration along the x - and y -axes, respectively. Each agent observes its own position, velocity, and lidar measurements of other agents and goals. As a consequence, the world model lacks sufficient information to accurately predict the next states. Specifically, the goal positions are not directly observed but are instead sensed through the lidar measurements. We believe this limitation significantly affects the performance of SHAC++.

Each agent receives a reward of 1 when it collects a goal. Thus, the maximum reward depends on the amount of time the agents have to collect the goals. For early stopping purposes, we set the maximum reward to k . Additionally, the reference line is set to k . While the transition function is differentiable, the reward function is not. Therefore, only PPO and SHAC++ are applicable to this scenario.

A.4 Sampling

In the Sampling task, n agents must collect rewards from a grid. The rewards are sampled from k Gaussian distributions. In Fig. 1d, the agents are represented by blue dots, while the k reward-generating Gaussians are displayed as a scalar field, where the intensity of the color represents the respective reward value.

Each agent has a continuous 2-dimensional action space, bounded between -1 and 1 , to represent acceleration along the x - and y -axes, respectively. Each agent observes its own position, velocity, lidar values from other agents, and rewards in a 3×3 grid around itself. As a consequence, the world model lacks sufficient information to accurately predict the next states. Specifically, it does not have access to the full reward distribution. We believe this limitation significantly affects the performance of SHAC++.

Each agent receives a reward equal to the value of the reward in the grid cell where it is located. Thus, the maximum reward depends on the placement of the Gaussians. Since the maximum reward varies across environments, we only plot a reference line representing good performance. While the reward function is differentiable, the one provided by VMAS is not. Therefore, we created a custom reward function to match the original one used by all algorithms (SHAC++, SHAC, and PPO).

B Architectures

As mentioned earlier, we test PPO, SHAC, SHAC++, and SHAC+ with two different architecture—Transformer and MLP. The former is a popular positional invariant architecture for sequence modeling [7]. While the latter is a simple feed-forward neural network.

The main advantage of the transformer architecture is its positional invariance property. In fact, the order in which the agent’s observation are fed into the network should not affect the ultimate outcome, at least, for the tested environments. We believe that this leads to better sample efficiency that it is ultimately observed in policies achieving higher rewards.

In contrast, the MLP is fed with a concatenation of all agent observations. This results in a simple and lightweight implementation, leading to faster inference times. However, in our experiments, the MLP appears to underperform compared to the transformer architecture.

(a) Attention matrix for the world model.

(b) Gradient norm for a transformer architecture wrt. a MLP architecture.

Figure 2: Network architecture visualizations: (left) attention pattern in the world model; (right) gradient norm comparison between transformer and MLP architectures.

B.1 Policy/Value/Reward MLP Network

When implementing the policy, value, and reward functions with an MLP, we use a single hidden layer with sizes of 32, 96, and 160, depending on the number of agents. This choice was made to account for the increasing complexity that a higher number of agents should introduce. The activation function is always ReLU, and dropout is used only for the policy network. The learning rate is consistently set to 0.001. The cache for training these networks is set to 30,000 samples. Gradient clipping is applied only to the policy network, with a threshold of 1. For a full list of hyperparameters, see Table 2 and Table 3.

B.2 Policy/Value/Reward Transformer Network

When implementing the policy, value, and reward functions with a transformer, we use a single hidden layer with a size of 64, regardless of the number of agents, and a feed-forward size of 128. We do not scale these sizes with the number of agents, as the transformer is expected to natively scale with the sequence length. The remaining hyperparameters are set consistently with those used in the MLP architecture. For a full list of hyperparameters, see Table 2 and Table 3.

B.3 World Model

When implementing the action world model, we consistently use a transformer architecture. Each action is represented as an embedding fed into the network. To maintain positional invariance between the agents, we employ a custom attention matrix that allows the action for step i of agent j , a_{ij} , to attend only to actions from the same step or previous steps of the same agent. Formally, a_{ij} can attend to all a_{kj} for $k < i$ and to all a_{ik} for $k \in \mathcal{N}$. This attention pattern is shown in Fig. 2a. As a result, the world models process sequences of length $32 \cdot n$. We use a slightly deeper architecture to account for the increased complexity of the task, with 3 layers. The hidden size is set to 64 and the feed-forward size to 128. The remaining hyperparameters are set consistently with those used in the MLP architecture. For a full list of hyperparameters, see Table 2.

C Additional Experiments

Finally, we present the results of the experiments with the MLP architecture in Fig. 3. We observe that the MLP architecture underperforms compared to the Transformer architecture. Nonetheless, SHAC++ often outperforms PPO and generally performs on par with SHAC.

Interestingly, the Discovery scenario appears to be the most challenging, as none of the algorithms (PPO and SHAC++) are able to make any meaningful progress. This may be caused by the sample inefficiency of the MLP architecture, combined with the fact that the world model cannot access the full state.

The only scenario where SHAC outperforms SHAC++ is the Transport scenario. This may be due to the MLP's inability to overcome the gradient noise from the world model.

To check also the scalability of SHAC++ we run the experiments with up to 20 agents in the Transport scenario. The results are shown in Fig. 3. We observe that SHAC++ is able to scale well with the number of agents, achieving good results even with 20 agents, also in this case similarly to SHAC.

Figure 3: Comparison between SHAC++, PPO, and SHAC for increasing number of agents for Dispersion, Transport, Discovery, and Sampling scenarios with the MLP architecture. We show the mean and standard deviation of the normalized rewards across 3 runs.

D Ablation Study

In the main paper, we focused on simultaneously replacing both the transition and reward functions with neural networks. This approach allows for greater generality and can be applied across a multitude of environments. However, when only the transition or reward function is differentiable and available, it is feasible to replace only one of them. This simplifies the algorithm, requiring the training of only a single additional network alongside the policy and value functions.

Specifically, we focus on replacing only the reward function. In fact, transition dynamics are often complex and challenging to model with a neural network, especially in multi-agent environments where observations depend not only on the actions of individual agents but also on those of other agents. This, in turn, may necessitate the use of larger architectures with greater computational demands, ultimately limiting the algorithm’s practicality.

In contrast, the reward function is often simpler and, therefore, easier to model using lightweight neural networks. Moreover, a high degree of

Figure 4: Comparison between SHAC++ and SHAC for increasing number of agents (up to 20) in the Transport scenario with the Transformer architecture. Results demonstrate the scalability of both approaches as the number of agents increases.

precision is typically not required in most scenarios. As a result, the reward function is an ideal candidate for replacement with a neural network.

This experiment also enables us to compare the final impact of gradients generated by a complex physics engine with those generated by a neural network. While the physics engine may produce more unstable gradients, the neural network may generate imprecise gradients, particularly during the early stages of training.

D.1 Results

We refer to the SHAC++ algorithm as SHAC+ when the transition function is differentiable and directly available. The results for the transformer architecture are shown in Fig. 5, while the results for the MLP architecture are presented in Fig. 6.

For the transformer architecture, SHAC++ generally appears to generate better policies, particularly in the Sampling and Transport environments. In the Dispersion environment, both algorithms perform comparably. Slightly better results are achieved with the SHAC+ algorithm in the Discovery environment.

For the MLP architecture, the results are more mixed. In the Dispersion environment, SHAC++ appears to achieve better policies. Conversely, in the Transport environment, SHAC+ leads to substantially better policies. In the Discovery environment, both policies struggle to produce meaningful results. Finally, in the Sampling environment, SHAC++ performs on par with SHAC+, except in the single-agent case, where SHAC+ struggles.

D.2 Discussion

We can easily observe that the transformer architecture leads, generally speaking, to better policies. This may be due to the positional invariance property of the transformers leading to more sample efficient networks.

Furthermore, with the transformer architecture, we observe a tendency for SHAC++ to produce better results. This may be attributed to the generated gradients being more stable, as shown in Fig. 2b.

In contrast, for the MLP architecture, the results are more mixed. This could be attributed to the MLP architecture being less sample-efficient, which ultimately leads to less accurate gradients.

Figure 5: Comparison between SHAC++ with and without transition network, labelled SHAC+, for increasing number of agents for Dispersion, Transport, Discovery, and Sampling scenarios. Transformer architecture.

Figure 6: Comparison between SHAC++ with and without transition network, labelled SHAC+, for increasing number of agents for Dispersion, Transport, Discovery, and Sampling scenarios. MLP architecture.

Parameter	Transformer	MLP
number of training environments	512	512
training horizon	32	32
number of evaluation environments	512	512
evaluation horizon	512	512
policy layers	1	1
policy hidden size	64	160, 32, 96
policy feedforward size	128	-
policy heads	1	-
policy dropout	0.1	0.1
policy activation	ReLU	ReLU
policy variance	1	1
value layers	1	1
value hidden size	64	160, 32, 96
value feedforward size	128	-
value dropout	0.0	0.0
value activation	ReLU	ReLU
reward layers	1	1
reward hidden size	64	160, 32, 96
reward feedforward size	128	-
reward dropout	0.0	0.0
reward activation	ReLU	ReLU
world layers	3	3
world hidden size	64	64
world feedforward size	128	128
world dropout	0.0	0.0
world activation	ReLU	ReLU
policy learning rate	0.001	0.001
reward learning rate	0.001	0.001
value learning rate	0.001	0.001
value clip coefficient	None	None
reward clip coefficient	None	None
policy clip coefficient	1	1
world cache size	30000	30000
reward cache size	30000	30000
value cache size	30000	30000
world/value/reward batch size	1000	1000
world/value/reward cooldown epochs	10	10
world cache bins	25	25
reward cache bins	9	9
value cache bins	9	9
α	1.0	1.0
early stopping - max reward fraction	0.9	0.9
early stopping - max envs fraction	0.9	0.9
seed	42, 43, 44	42, 43, 44
max episodes	20000	20000
epochs between environment resets	10	10
epochs between evaluations	100	100
γ	0.99	0.99
λ	0.95	0.95

Table 2: SHAC/SHAC++/SHAC+ Hyperparameters

Parameter	Transformer	MLP
number of training environments	512	512
training horizon	32	32
number of evaluation environments	512	512
evaluation horizon	512	512
policy layers	1	1
policy hidden size	64	160, 32, 96
policy feedforward size	128	-
policy heads	1	-
policy dropout	0.1	0.1
policy activation	ReLU	ReLU
policy variance	1	1
value layers	1	1
value hidden size	64	160, 32, 96
value feedforward size	128	-
value dropout	0.0	0.0
value activation	ReLU	ReLU
policy learning rate	0.001	0.001
value learning rate	0.001	0.001
early stopping - max reward fraction	0.9	0.9
early stopping - max envs fraction	0.9	0.9
seed	42, 43, 44	42, 43, 44
max episodes	20000	20000
epochs between environment resets	10	10
epochs between evaluations	100	100
γ	0.99	0.99
λ	0.95	0.95
α	1.0	1.0

Table 3: PPO Hyperparameters

References

- [1] E. Coumans. Pybullet, a python module for physics simulation for games, robotics and machine learning, 2017.
- [2] A. Gupta, R. Kumar, M. Egorov, and S. Levine. Multi-agent reinforcement learning in mixed cooperative-competitive environments. In *Proceedings of the 35th AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, pages 11093–11100, 2021.
- [3] J. Z. Leibo, E. A. Dueñez-Guzmán, A. S. Vezhnevets, J. P. Agapiou, P. Sunehag, R. Koster, J. Matyas, C. Beattie, I. Mordatch, and T. Graepel. Scalable evaluation of multi-agent reinforcement learning with melting pot. In *Proceedings of the 38th International Conference on Machine Learning*, volume 139, pages 6187–6199, 2021.
- [4] M. e. a. Samvelyan. The starcraft multi-agent challenge. In *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Autonomous Agents and MultiAgent Systems*, pages 2186–2188, 2019.
- [5] J. Suarez, Y. Du, P. Isola, and I. Mordatch. Neural mmo: A massively multiagent game environment for training and evaluating intelligent agents. In *Proceedings of the 33rd AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, pages 4476–4483, 2019.
- [6] J. K. e. a. Terry. Pettingzoo: Gym for multi-agent reinforcement learning. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 34, pages 15032–15043, 2021.
- [7] A. Vaswani. Attention is all you need. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2017.